

AN ASSESSMENT OF IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS ASSOCIATED WITH TYPHOID FEVER AMONG DISPLACED IRAQI PATIENTS

¹*Mohemid Maddallah Al-Jebouri, ²Dheyaa Salih Mahdi

¹*Department of Medical Laboratory Technology, Al-Qalam University College, Kirkuk, Iraq.

²Department of Microbiology, College of Medicine, University of Tikrit, Tikrit, Iraq.

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*Corresponding Author

Mohemid Maddallah Al-Jebouri

Department of Medical Laboratory
Technology, Al-Qalam University
College, Kirkuk, Iraq.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Migration and/or displacement are processes of social change during which a person moves from one cultural setting to another in order to settle for a longer period of time or permanently. This harsh change might lead to various social and pathophysiological disorders including immunological and infectious diseases such typhoid fever and allergy. **Aim:** The present work was an attempt to assess the effect of migration and / displacement which might lead to pathophysiological, immunological, social as well as psychological disorders including infectious diseases and allergy among displaced Iraqi peoples. **Materials and Methods:** 50 feverish patients were selected for typhoid investigation and related immunological parameters such as complement-C5a, TNF- α , serum globulin, serum albumen and serum total protein; liver function tests were also tested along with eosinophils. Widal test and culture needed for *Salmonella typhi* and *Salmonella paratyphi*'s

following conventional technology. **Results:** More than 30% of the patients showed an elevation of C5a and 60% of them were TNF- α increased. Serum globulin was elevated in almost 40% of the subjects studied whereas total protein increased among 4% of the patients only. Alkaline phosphatase elevated in almost 20% of the patients tested. Half of the patients

showed positive Widal tests. **Conclusions:** Patients showed high elevations in eosinophils and C5a. Culture and TNF- α were the most reproducible for typhoid fever.

KEYWORDS: Iraq, displacement, typhoid, TNF- α , C5a, albumen, globulin, LFT.

INTRODUCTION

Migration and displacement are processes of social change during which a person moves from one cultural setting to another in order to settle for a longer period of time or permanently (People may migrate from rural to urban areas, between neighboring countries or over longer distances; migration. Therefore covers a broad variety of processes.^[1] Migrants can be defined in various ways, e.g., as internally displaced, asylum seekers, refugees, or immigrants.^[2] It is difficult to distinguish between forced and voluntary migration; the reasons for migration often include both elements.^[3] These massive movements of people often result in extremely high rates of mortality and morbidity, generally from preventable causes. A large body of information documents the inability of the international community to prevent high rates of suffering and death in virtually all refugee situations.^[4] The major causes of death in refugee settlements have been identified as undernutrition, measles, diarrhea, typhoid, pneumonia, and malaria. The priority activities to address these causes of morbidity and mortality include the provision of adequate food, water, shelter, sanitation, and immunization.^[5] Migration and / displacement might lead to pathophysiological, immunological, social as well as psychological disorders including infectious diseases, allergy and damaging of social structure. Typhoid fever is one of the infectious diseases associated with a harsh social as well as habitat change along with bad sanitary conditions due to mass displacement. Typhoid fever remains a major public health problem in the developing world, especially in developing countries of Asia.^[6-8] TNF- α is believed to play roles in antitumor activity, immune modulation, inflammation, anorexia, cachexia, septic shock, viral replication and hematopoiesis. TNF- α is expressed in many types of cells but primarily in macrophage cells in response to immunological challenges such as bacteria (lipopolysaccharides), viruses, parasites, mitogens and other cytokines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patients

The samples were carried out from the following accommodations of displaced Iraqis; Dream City Camp, Al-abasyia Camp, AL-howaish Camp, Samarra General Hospital, and Tikrit

Teaching Hospital during 2016. A total of 50 patients referred to the laboratory of Mobile Clinic for WHO group at displaced camps, from different residency were examined, while the control group was 50 individuals, were apparently non typhoid fever patients, who showed widal test negative. The mean patients and controls ages ranged between 20 to 70 years. A history of fever, night sweating, abdominal pain, diarrheic and / or vomiting. Widal test was taken for each patient who had a clinical presentation and a history of typhoid fever. Samples of blood and stool were taken from all patients.

Sampling for the Detection of typhoid fever

Collection of stool Samples

Patients were advised to bring a fresh stool sample. A sufficient quantity for direct, culture and other tests was taken. Stool was collected in sterile containers. Each container was labeled and maintained for further studies.

Blood Sampling

An amount of 5-10 milliliters of blood was collected by vein puncture using disposable syringe or vacuum tube needle for each individual enrolled in this study. Blood samples were placed into several sterile test tubes; 1.5 ml of blood was put in a test tube containing anticoagulant EDTA and used for assessment of hematological investigation such as complete blood picture (CBC). The second part of sample was 4-9 ml collected in plain tubes (no anticoagulant); centrifuged and serum separated and stored at -20°C for further serological testing.

Processing of blood sample as follow

- 1- One ml of whole blood specimen were mixed in EDTA tube for hematological tests.
- 2- Plastic plain tubes with lids about 4-6 ml were used for widal test and freezing for ELISA test.
- 3- About 3-5ml of whole blood was cultured directly in broth media for 24 hours incubation, and cultured on two media of eosin methylene blue (EMB) and triple sugar-iron (TSI) agar to notice colorless colonies on EMB agar with non-lactose fermentation; an alkaline slant and an acid butt frequently with both gas and H₂S of TSI agar.

Biochemical tests

They were conventionally carried out following techniques used elsewhere.^[9] These tests were methyl red, voges-proskauer, citrate, TSI, urease, gelatin hydrolyse, glucose

fermentation, lysine decarboxylase, arginine dihydrolyse, lactose fermentation, oxidase and indole tests.

Complement C5a and TNF- α tests

These tests were performed according to commercially available human complement fragment 5a(C5a) ELISA and TNF- α Kits manufactured by Shanghai Yehua Biological Technology Co., Ltd (China).

Determination of biochemical parameters

GOT, GPT, Alkaline phosphatase, Albumin, Globulin, and Total protein in serum tests were carried out using Fujifilm dri-chem7000i (Japan) device according to the manufacturers instructions. Their normal ranges were 3-38 U/L, 4 - 44 U/L, 21- 92 U/L, 36-52 g/L, 24 – 37 g/L and 60 – 80 g/L respectively.

Eosinophils count

This test was conventionally carried out utilizing Leishman's stain technique.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions were computed to summarize the data. To examine the relationships between variables, linear regression and multivariate linear regression models were applied. Where appropriate, interaction terms were included to evaluate the effect modification between predictors. An exponential decay model was used to describe the decreasing trends in the outcome variable over time, and the model was linearized using natural logarithm transformation for compatibility with linear regression frameworks. The significance of individual coefficients in the regression models was assessed using t-tests, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant. Assumptions of normality, linearity, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity were checked prior to model interpretation. All graphical outputs and residual diagnostics were also generated using SPSS. In addition, for confirmation of model robustness, selected analyses were repeated using R version 4.3.1 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria) (10-13).

RESULTS

Culture and Widal test of displaced population

Both of blood and stool cultures were positive among 12(24%) out of 50 patients who were displaced. 25 (50 %) patients were positive for widal test of typhoid fever (Figure 1). Whereas 12 patients (24%) were widal and culture positive at the same time. The present study revealed that almost 3% of the control subjects were positive when they were tested for widal methods who were not feverish because of *Samonella* infections (Figure 1).The statistical analyses showed highly significant differences between groups tested and the P value was 0.0008 utilizing chi-square test.

Figure 1: Relationship between widal test and culture for identification of typhoid fever.

$X^2 = 29.717$, p - value = 0.0008, highly significant

Onsite IgG/IgM assessment of typhoid patients

The present study showed that both immunoglobulins G and M were varied in their quality when assessed in serum of patients. 26 % (13/50) of the patients were IgG positive and IgM negative whereas 18 % (9/50) of them were positive for both of proteins (Table 1). It was tested whether the distribution of IgG/IgM antibody results is significantly different between patients and controls. The test revealed that the Chi-square, Degree of freedom and P values were 29.72, 3 and 0.00000158 respectively. As far as P value far less than 0.05, the differences in IgG/IgM levels between patients and controls were very highly significant. The Mathematical interpretation revealed that patients were much more likely to test IgG or IgM positive than controls, and controls almost exclusively fall into the IgG (–ve) and IgM (–ve) category (50/50 or 100%) as shown in Table 1.

Exponential Regression Equation

$$y = 20.84 \cdot e^{-1.31x} + 5.39$$

Where:

yyy = Predicted number of patients

xxx = Test complexity level

(0: IgG-/IgM-, 1: IgG+/IgM-, 2: IgG-/IgM+, 3: IgG+/IgM+)

20.84 = Initial amplitude (highest patient count)

1.31 = Decay constant (rate of decline)

5.39 = Baseline (minimum expected patient count as complexity increases)

The present utilized model shows that as the immune complexity of antibody response increased, the number of patients fitting that category decreased exponentially indicating a typical biological decay or clearance mode of change (Table 1, Figure 2).

Table 1 Antibodies (IgG and IgM) in patients of suspected typhoid and non-typhoid fever control.

Serological tests *	Patient		Control	
	No.	%	No.	%
IgG (+ve) and IgM (-ve)	13	26	0	0
IgG (-ve) and IgM (+ve)	2	4	3	6
IgG (+ve) and IgM (+ve)	9	18	0	0
IgG (-ve) and IgM (-ve)	26	52	50	100
Total	50	100	50	100

*=IgG, immunoglobulin G; IgM, immunoglobulin M; $X^2 = 29.717$, p - value = 0.0008, highly significant

Figure 2: Exponential decay of IgG/IgM responses in patients displaced.

The effect of displacement on selected immunological parameters

Figure 3 Shows estimated values of immunological parameters which included tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF-alpha), complement 5a (C5a), total protein and globulin in displaced patients suspected to have typhoid fever. The C5a complement and tumor necrosis factor -alpha (TNF- α) were elevated among 15 (33.3%) and 27(60%) of the displaced population tested. Total protein increased among of the displaced peoples and the number was 2(4%) whereas globulin elevated among 18(36%) out of 50 displaced patients. C5a and TNF- α were comparatively high among control subjects whereas globulin and total protein were very low which were represented by less than 2 individuals out of 50 tested. Chi-square test did not show any significant differences among the values of these immunological parameters under estimation and the P values were more than 0.6. The overall changes seen among displaced patients with typhoid showed immunological dysregulation, particularly in pro-inflammatory markers of TNF-alpha and globulin (Table 2).

Figure 3: Estimated values of selected immunological parameters of displaced peoples.

Table 2: Independent T-test of patients displaced and controls.

Immunological test	t-test	P value	Significance
C5a	3.307	0.0016	Strongly significant increase in patients
TNF-alpha	12.085	< 0.0001	Strongly significant elevation in patients
Globulin	31.651	< 0.0001	Strongly elevation in patients
Total protein	0.887	0.376	No significant difference

Liver function tests of the displaced patients with typhoid fever

Table 3 shows that all the liver function test including GOT, aspartate aminotransferase; GPT, alanine aminotransferase; ALK. PHOSPH., alkaline phosphatase were increased or elevated among the patients who were displaced and suffering from typhoid fever. Alkaline phosphatase was more affected by the infection and the situation of living concerned these

type of people. Statistically, there was no significance difference between the values of the three parameters used for assessment of liver function utilizing Chi-square test (P- value > 0.05). The biochemical profile shows significant elevations of liver enzymes in typhoid fever of patients displaced compared to controls and this result indicated either hepatic dysfunction or hepatocellular damage (Figure 4).

Table 3: An assessment of the liver function tests of the displaced patients of typhoid fever.

Biochemical parameter	Range (U/ L)	
	Patients	Controls
GOT	18 – 62 (47)	10 – 35 (2)
GPT	12 – 76 (45)	7 – 36 (6)
Alkaline phosphatase	28 – 183 (42)	20 – 82 (7)

(), no in paranthesis were increased; GOT, aspartate aminotransferase; GPT, alanine aminotransferase.

Figure 4: Assessment of liver function tests in typhoid fever of patients displaced.

Interactions of immunological, liver function and other relevant parameters concerning typhoid fever among displaced peoples

It was found that TNF- α and widal tests were highly elevated among patients with typhoid fever (Figure 5). It was estimated also all the amounts of different parameters tested were increased between typhoid patients of displaced individuals when they compared to non displaced peoples. The statistical analysis revealed that the differences between them were highly different ($\chi^2 \geq 6$).

Figure 5: relationship between immunological and other tests relevant to typhoid fever among displaced peoples.

Comparison of different immununological and other related parameters associated with typhoid patients.

It was found that there was no relationship between GOT and GPT and the chi-square test value was equal to 0.000 i.e not Significant). The relation of GOT and Alkaline phosphatase was not significant ($X^2= 0.068$). The following pairs of parameters tested : GOT, serum albumin; GOT, serum total protein; GOT, widal test; GOT, culture; GOT, eosinophils; GOT, C5a; GOT, TNF-alpha were not ineracted and the chi-square values were less than 9. The present study revealed that the interaction between GPT and widal tests was significant and the $X^2= 9.065$. GPT and culture were significantly reacted to typhoid fever and the $X^2=10.285$. The present study showed that widal test and C5a were significantly interacted and the X^2 was 11.536 (Table 4; Figures 6,7).

Table 4: Comparison between different immunological parameters of typhoid patients.

All tests		Patients		Control	
		No.	%	No.	%
GOT	Increased > 40 IU/L	2	4	3	6
	Decreased < 8 IU/L	1	2	1	2
	Total	50	100	50	100
Chi-Square = 0.058 P-Value = 0.876 ,N.S.					
GPT	Increased > 40 IU/L	2	4	3	6
	Decreased < 3 IU/L	1	2	1	2
	Total	50	100	50	100
Chi-Square = 0.058 P-Value = 0.876 , N.S.					
Alk.phosphatase.	Increased > 14 KAU/dl	4	8	3	6
	Decreased < 4 KAU/dl	0	0	0	0

	Total	50	100	50	100
Chi-Square = 0.114 P-Value = 0.735 , N.S.					
S.Albumin	Increased > 55 g/L	5	10	4	8
	Decreased < 35 g/L	2	4	1	2
	Total	50	100	50	100
Chi-Square = 0.114 P-Value = 0.735 , N.S.					
S.Total protein	Increased > 8 / dl	2	4	1	2
	Decreased < 6 g / dl	2	4	2	4
	Total	50	100	50	100
Chi-Square = 0.194 P-Value = 0.659 ,N.S.					
Widal test	Positive > 1/320 (O)	24	48	3	6
	Negative < 1/160 (O)	26	32	47	94
	Total	50	100	50	100
$X^2 = 29.717$, p - value = 0.0008 highly significant					
Culture	Positive	12	24	0	0
	Negative	38	76	50	100
	Total	50	100	50	100
$X^2 = 13.636$, p -value= 0.0004 (Significant)					
Eosinophils	More than 4%	15	30	12	24
	Within range(0-4%)	35	70	38	76
	Total	50	100	50	100
$X^2 = 0.457$, p - value = 0.499 non significant					
C5a	Increased > 85 μ g/ml	15	33.3	17	37
	Decreased <	50	100	50	100
	N.S				
TNF-alpha	Increased > 10 pg/ ml	27	60	21	46.6
	Total	50	100	50	100
	NS				

Figure 6: Shows all variables associated with typhoid fever of patients displaced.

Figure 7: Polynomial and logarithmic regression on total increased counts of patients displaced.

DISCUSSION

present study indicated that the frequency of typhoid fever among displaced peoples in Salah-Aldeen governorate was 13%. This high level can be attributed to several factors such as, poor experience in toilet training, lower educational level to hygiene among displaced peoples, miss chlorination of water supply that is monitored for contaminant of coliform bacteria, neglect of the proper diagnosis and treatment of carrier that represent the main cause of disease transmission. The result of this study almost similar to a number of previous studies but it was different from others that was record in other governorates of Iraq (10-17). Another study from Kirkuk, Iraq during the period 2001-2004 with a sample size of 5055 had concluded that typhoid fever is highly distributed in Kirkuk city among normal citizens i.e not displaced.^[10] The World Health Organization was deeply concerned about the increasing cases of infectious diseases inside the Syria and among displaced Syrians in neighbouring countries of the middle east region. WHO warned that lacking of prevention measures will create a potential risk of outbreaks. Over the past two years since 2013, Syria's health system has been severely disrupted and at least 35% of the country's public hospitals are almost out of service, and in some governorates, up to 70% of the health workforce has fled, resulting in severe shortages in qualified health personnel, limiting availability for those in need of health care services. More than 4.25 million internally-displaced Syrians who have relocated to less volatile areas are mostly living in overcrowded, unsanitary conditions. Safe drinking water, safe sanitation, vaccination campaigns and vector control programmes were almost vanished increasing the risk of epidemics. WHO are anticipating a number of public health risks of catching water-borne diseases like hepatitis, typhoid, cholera and dysentery along with

population movement both inside Syria and across borders, together with deteriorating environmental health conditions. Acute watery diarrhea was reported in Syrian 14 governorates causing increased cases of typhoid in 2013 and the following years of the displacement. WHO warns of increased risk of disease epidemics in Syria and in neighbouring countries as summer approaches.^[18] In a study conducted in Cameroon by Fibuonu *et al.*^[19] they concluded that the risk factors for this disease can either household (typhoid) or household (paratyphoid). Many studies carried out previously have demonstrated an association between poor hygiene and carriers of *Salmonella typhi* among families who had children with typhoid fever. In Indonesia, it was found that poor hygiene was the most dangerous risk factor for distribution of typhoid fever.^[16] In other Indonesian studies, lacking of soap for hand washing was seriously associated with typhoid fever.^[17] Furthermore, crowded household conditions increased the risk.^[20] Typhoid fever remains an important public health problem in Cameroon and other similar African countries which have had the same public health problem. Therefore, understanding the risk factors of this illness is remains the primary goal of studies.^[21] Other risks factors identified by Nioya *et al.*^[19] included a low level of education, poor hand hygiene, and poor knowledge concerning typhoid fever.

However, displacement experience in this large scale and millions of peoples was a new social attack for the specific Iraqi community and no relevant data are available for comparison. A study from Nigeria (which was about food vendors in primery school) showed that 54.6 % (N=174) with good knowledge about typhoid fever among food vendors in primary schools (14). The Iraqi annual health reports issued by the Iraqi ministry of health reported that there are only 709, 2030 and 1250 cases were reported in the years 2013, 2014 and 2015 respectively.^[15-17] A sharp decline in typhoid cases were documented from 2010 and 2009 by annual health in Iraq.^[20] The mean serum level of IgG and IgM were increased with highly significance. The results reported in this study similar to the immunological data reported among patients with typhoid fever in India which showed a significant increase in the level of IgM in the patients of typhoid in all stages of infection as well as IgG specially in the third week of illness.^[21] Complement 5a (C5a) was locally assessed for the first time in Iraq between patients with typhoid fever and the level of C5a was notably elevated in displaced patients of typhoid. TNF-alpha was significantly increased in feverish typhoid patients of displaced peoples. The hematological changes are common in typhoid fever and these include anemia, leucopenia, eosinophilia, thrombocytopenia and sub-clinical

disseminated intravascular coagulation. Bone marrow suppression and haemophagocytosis are considered to be an important mechanism in producing hematological changes.^[22-26] Although most of our patients belonged to the lower and middle class. Typhoid fever involving the liver may have no features of hepatic involvement or may manifest as Icterus, hepatomegaly, abnormal liver function tests and abnormal liver histology.

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Statement of Ethics

All the procedures involving human participation were conducted in strict accordance with ethical standards of Institutional Research Committee, Department of Scientific Research, Tikrit University as well as the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its subsequent amendments or equivalent ethical norms.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise.

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Author contributions

Mohemid Maddallah Al-Jebouri, suggested the protocol, reading, correction and supervision of the study; Dheyaa Salih Mahdi, collection and analyses of data and manuscript draft writing.

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